

A STUDY ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN KRISHNA DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH

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ABSTRACT:

The study examined women entrepreneurs in order to find the Socio-Economic conditions such as distribution of age, marital status, Educational qualification, nature of business, nature of commencement, type of ownership, nature of family, reasons for commencement, sources of funds etc. It also analysed the level and the development of women entrepreneurs in Krishna district. It observed that growth and prosperity of our national can be achieved only through process of industrialization since women are the major sources of man power in our country they should be encouraged to become entrepreneurs. The competitive spirit should be instilled in them from their childhood.

KEY WORDS: Women, entrepreneur, Socio-Economic conditions, development.
